

IMPLEMENTING TRANSFORMATIVE LEARNING INTO ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

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A theory of education put forth by Professor Jack Mezirow in the 1970s and subsequently revised and discussed is known as transformative learning. It emphasizes the value of communication and reflection while taking a constructivist stance on learning, which holds that meaning is built from experience and internal knowledge. Students use these methods of instruction to question their own "meaning perspectives," or implicit worldviews. Meaningful views are the individual points of view that encompass our beliefs on the world, society, and the development of knowledge, as well as our beliefs regarding our own skills and the world around us.

According to Mezirow, a "disorienting dilemma," or circumstance that tests one's worldview, is necessary for adults to participate in transformational learning. Those who are willing to go through the agony and suffering with me can start to see things from a different perspective. The next step is to absorb and apply this new perspective on life.

Some of the meaning views may be somewhat straightforward, such as the idea that a specific procedure is optimal for a given job. Class, racial, religious, and gender-based views are examples of more fundamental ones. No matter how you slice it, these beliefs run deep and seldom challenged.

Students' meaning perspectives might be a hurdle to acceptance in adult education, as shown in the two overlapping magnifying glasses graphic. If what a learner is learning is consistent with their existing worldview, then the material will

enrich and perhaps strengthen their viewpoint. Some pupils could dismiss it because they don't think it aligns with their worldview. However, a teacher cannot ensure that each student has a life-changing educational experience. They can only set the stage, supply the resources, and offer words of encouragement.

Teachers can better pave the way for life-altering educational opportunities if they do the following:

- Make sure that students feel comfortable enough to voice their opinions on the subject.
- Think of interesting ways to convey the topic so that students can make sense of it on their own, like using simulations, case studies, or role plays.
- Initiate class discussions by having students share their thoughts on the topic.
- Give them a place to think, and let them know if their views have changed, so they may reflect on it.

It is one thing to understand the concept of transformative learning and quite another to actually implement it. In many contexts, such as problem-solving, education and training, organizational culture, individual growth, and leadership, there are tangible approaches to promote a transformative learning technique.

Solving Complex Problems

It is possible to impede the efficient and effective resolution of problems by becoming mired in one's own meaning perspective. Now is an ideal moment to welcome transformative learning, whether you're working through anything alone or with a group.

- Start by generating a list of potential ideas.
- Let go of preconceived notions of what is "right" and be willing to learn from your mistakes
- Try to think outside of the box and see if you can come up with any creative alternatives.
- Contemplate the reasons behind the successes and failures.

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